

PROCESS INDUCED DEFORMATION OF AIRCRAFT STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS

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1 Introduction

Residual stresses and deformations are important concerns in composite manufacturing for the aerospace industry. They can lead to a reduction of structure performance, such as strength and fatigue life, and can initiate cracks in the matrix. The assembly of angled composite structures with deformations can be problematic or impossible, leading to part rejections.

The sources of residual stresses and their effects on composite structures have been widely investigated for over three decades and overall, four main mechanisms have been identified [1-2]: thermal strains [3-5], resin shrinkage [5-9], tool-part interaction [10-12] and temperature/degree-of-cure/fibre volume fraction gradients [13-14]. These mechanisms can lead to dimensional changes such as spring-in, warpage and/or thickness variations. Secondary effects, such as cure cycle and cooling rate were also investigated in the literature [10-11,15-16]. A two-hold cycle with gelation occurring at the end of the first hold produced more spring-in than a one-hold cycle. However, the effect of cooling rate was negligible on the part deformations.

Typically, for thin symmetric/balanced laminates, the most important source of part deformation is often caused by the thermal strains and difference of coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between the composite and the tool/mandrel. This leads to tool growth and spring-in.

Sources of part deformations act simultaneously during processing. They are complex and time-consuming to investigate experimentally. It is therefore recommended to combine focused experimental testing and modelling software to

increase confidence and reduce uncertainty. This approach will help to: a) identify the key mechanisms in part dimensional changes, b) propose a tool compensation scheme to avoid unwanted part deformations, and c) reduce manufacturing time and costs of complex composite parts.

At Bombardier Aerospace, numerical simulation such as process induced deformation study is implemented to validate both tool design and manufacturing process parameters prior to actual fabrication of parts, resulting in significant cost savings by minimizing experimental trials and errors. In this work, the deformations of a C-frame structural component manufactured by resin transfer moulding (RTM) was investigated. Four parts were moulded according to two different cure cycles and simulations were performed to predict process-induced dimensional changes based on material property models. Predicted and experimental results were compared using a coordinate measuring machine (CMM) for spring-in and twist measurements.

2 Procedures

2.1 Materials

The resin used for this work was a commercially available RTM resin system, CYCOM 890 from Cytec, and fibres used were carbon fibre based 5HS and Non Crimp Fabric (NCF).

2.2 Manufacturing Process

RTM process was used to fabricate the C-shape frames. A three piece RTM mould was utilized with an internal mandrel, as shown on Fig. 1. This matched RTM tooling creates two finished surfaces, which provides an improved dimensional accuracy.

By means of compaction generated by the mandrel expansion during cure, it was feasible to achieve high fibre volume fraction.

The dry fabric with plasticizer was laid up as per the following laminate configuration: $[5HS(\pm 45), NCF(0,90)]_s$. The materials were then heated under vacuum. When cooled and debagged, the preform stack up was then positioned in the mandrel. The mandrel was placed into the tool cavity after which the tool was closed. A vacuum was maintained within the moulds cavity and pressurized resin was allowed to flow into the cavity. Injected resin has low viscosity at the injection temperature which allows for faster flow rates and easier wetting of the reinforcing material. The tool was heated and the part was allowed to cure while the resin remains pressurized. Once the cure time has elapsed, cooling cycle and demoulding operation starts at the same time. When demoulded from the tool, the cured part stays with the mandrel and cooled under ambient conditions. The part was then removed from the mandrel and trimmed. The final thickness of the part, based on the mould cavity, is estimated to be 1.778 mm (0.070”).

As part of the objectives of this work, the effects of processing parameters on the part deformation were studied. The injection temperature was varied to understand the effect on final part deformation. The heat up rates were kept the same for both situations. The variable cure parameters are listed in Table 1.

2.3 Simulations

Residual stresses simulations were performed with Abaqus 6.11 and COMPRO Common Component Architecture (CCA) to predict part deformations after demoulding. The C-frame layup, $[5HS(\pm 45), NCF(0,90)]_s$, was modelled with 8 layers of the same thickness as $[+45,-45,0,90]_s$. Two models including the mould, mandrel and part were developed: a cross-sectional area with a thickness of 5 mm (Fig. 2) and a full 3D model (Fig. 3). Assuming symmetry along the XZ plane allowed us to reduce the models to half-sections. The cross-section model was used to quickly obtain preliminary results related to optimization of material properties and cooldown parameters. Table

2 lists the cooldown rates and heat transfer coefficients (HTC), selected as per the manufacturer's recommendation. The full 3D model was used to analyze twist, radius changes and spring-in variations of the C-angles along the length of the frame.

For both models, symmetrical boundary conditions (BC) were applied on the XZ and YZ planes (see Fig. 2). Friction contact between mould-part and part-mandrel was simulated with a coefficient of 0.3 and debonding was allowed to accommodate resin shrinkage. The mould's elements were deactivated during cooldown and the mandrel's elements and symmetrical BCs were deactivated during demoulding at room temperature. Material property models for 890RTM epoxy and carbon fibre were taken from Khoun [1] and implemented into COMPRO CCA.

To further reduce computing time, a single simplified cure cycle was used for simulations. Residual stresses developed before gelation are released, whereas those generated after gelation are locked in and subsequently cause process-induced deformations. Based on the cure kinetics model of the 890RTM epoxy presented by Khoun et al. [2], it was estimated that gelation (at $\alpha = 0.7$) occurred during the 3 hr-hold regardless of cure cycle (as presented in Table 1) and that consequently, the heating step could be eliminated from the simulations. The resulting cure cycle and main steps are summarized in Fig. 4. At the beginning of the 3 hr-hold step, an initial degree of cure of 0.7 was assumed. The mould was removed at 180°C (355°F) before the cooldown step to allow for easier demoulding of the C-frame on the mandrel at room temperature.

Particular attention was given to CTE characterization for the fibre/resin system used in this work. CTE was measured with a TA Instruments TMA Q400 thermo-mechanical analyzer. 4.3 mm-thick flat plates made of 16 plies of unidirectional NCF and 890RTM epoxy resin were manufactured and cut into 1 cm x 1 cm square samples. The samples were submitted to 3 heating cycles from 40°C to 250°C, at a rate of 3°C/min. Tests were performed on 2 to 3 specimens in

directions shown on Fig. 5 to obtain CTE values in-plane (CTE_{L1} and CTE_{L2}) and transversely (CTE_t).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Thermal Expansion Characterization

Fig. 6 shows typical TMA results in transverse direction of a unidirectional NCF/890RTM epoxy sample. The CTE was measured between 50°C and 150°C for all samples and average values were calculated. The following results were obtained (standard deviation): $CTE_{L1} = 6.61 \times 10^{-8} / ^\circ\text{C}$ (3.49×10^{-8}), $CTE_{L2} = 3.73 \times 10^{-5} / ^\circ\text{C}$ (0.11×10^{-5}) and $CTE_t = 4.24 \times 10^{-5} / ^\circ\text{C}$ (0.00×10^{-5}). For simulation purposes, it was assumed that CTE_t was equal to CTE_{L2} and that those values were constant with temperature, given that the processing temperature was at most equal to the glass-transition temperature. A lumped CTE model for the unidirectional lamina was implemented into COMPRO CCA based on CTE_{L1} and CTE_{L2} values.

3.2 Part Deformation Simulations

3.2.1 Cross-Sectional Model

Fig. 7 shows the C-frame before (left) and after demoulding (right) for a typical cross-sectional simulation. Deformations were evaluated in 2 ways: 1) difference between d_1 and d_2 , Δd ; and 2) spring-in angle δ . Table 3 summarizes Δd and δ values for all cooldown parameters investigated. The spring-in angles varied between 0.91° and 0.89° as linear cooldown rate increased. The negligible effect of cooling parameters was previously observed in the literature as well [15-16]. HTC did not have any noticeable effect on the deformations either, but results remained similar to those obtained at different cooldown rates. In practice, part deformations also depend on the quality of manufacturing and consequently, variations of 0.02° in predicted values are insignificant.

These values were compared to a simple analytical equation developed by Radford to calculate the spring-in of 2D angled parts [5,17]:

$$\delta = \phi \frac{(CTE_{L1} - CTE_t)\Delta T}{1 + CTE_t\Delta T} \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the initial angle of the part and ΔT is the temperature difference during cooldown. For $\phi = 90^\circ$ and $\Delta T = 160^\circ\text{C}$, δ is equal to 0.80°. This value is reasonably close to results presented in Table 3, considering it ignores resin shrinkage and mould-part-mandrel interactions [1].

3.2.2 3D C-Frame Model

Results presented in Section 3.2.1 for the cross-section model showed that the cooldown rate had little effect on the part deformations. Therefore, for the 3D C-frame model, only one cooldown condition was investigated: 2-hour cooldown at a rate of 1.9°C/min.

Fig. 8 illustrates the deformed shape of the C-frame after demoulding for a scale deformation factor equal to 10. The legend shows the deformation magnitude, U , in meters. Spring-in was measured and calculated in the same way as presented for the cross-section model, but for 3 sections along the length of the C-frame (Fig. 8a). The twist was quantified as an angle, θ . To calculate it, two lines were drawn on the web of the frame between points 1-2 and 1'-2', as seen on Fig. 8b. Line 1-2 was translated to point 2' to have the same origin as line 1'-2'. Finally, line 1-2 was projected on the same plane as line 1'-2' and θ was calculated as the angle between these two lines (Fig. 8b, bottom).

Table 4 lists the deformation values for spring-in and twist. Δd varies between 0.86 mm and 1.14 mm, which approximately corresponds to angles δ from 0.75° to 1.0°. These results are within the same range as presented in Section 3.2.1 for the cross-section, but they show that spring-in is smaller in the middle section than at the ends. Moreover, the deformation of the top flange in all three sections is slightly more significant than the bottom flange due to the change of curvature. The twist angle θ between both extremities of the frame is equal to +2.1°, calculated from line 1-2 to line 1'-2'.

3.3 Experimental Results

Two C-frames were manufactured for each cure cycle (Study A and Study B as listed in Table 1). Fig. 9a shows two parts after demoulding and Fig. 9b, after trimming. Visually, no major differences were identified between parts manufactured with both cure cycles.

The frames were measured using a Mitutoya Crysta-ApexC CMM. The Head was a Renishaw PH10MQ SP25M, and to reach inside the C-frame a SM25-2 4mm probe was used. The parts were measured at five different cross-sections and along the length of each flange on the outer surface. The data were exported into CATIA and combined to partially redraw the parts in 3 dimensions for comparison with the simulations. An example is illustrated on Fig. 10. These measurements allowed for the quantification of spring-in (Δd , δ) and twist (θ).

In terms of experimental spring-in, studies A and B both led to similar results, with a maximum difference of 0.36% between the highest and lowest Δd values. It indicates excellent reproducibility of the processing method and the non-dependency of cure cycle on spring-in deformations within the sample size presented in this work. In terms of twist, a maximum difference of 53% in the angle θ was calculated between the four parts. However, no specific trend was observed between studies A and B, suggesting that twist is a type of deformation that is more difficult to control and does not depend on cure cycle.

Table 5 lists the main deformation results, averaged over the four parts, for cross-sections 1, 3 and 5. Approximate corresponding values for the 3D simulation are reported as well for comparison. Experimentally, greater spring-in was observed at the extremities, as predicted through simulations. Angles δ_1 and δ_3 show very good agreement with predictions, but δ_5 is larger by 0.28° for the manufactured parts. The C-frames generally exhibit greater spring-in on the top flange due to the curvature effect, but the difference with the bottom flange remains low ($\Delta d < 0.04$ mm). The twist angle, θ , is equal to $1.05^\circ (\pm 0.22^\circ)$, which falls within the predicted value of 1.20° .

Generally, the deformations assessed on the manufactured C-frames are similar to what was predicted through Abaqus/COMPRO simulations. Small variations were however observed, especially for spring-in measured at cross-section 5. Several factors may have contributed to such discrepancies: improper definition of boundary conditions after demoulding, manufacturing defects, such as inconsistent thickness, resin-rich regions or fibre distortions. More components should be manufactured to obtain a larger sample size for simulation optimization.

4 Conclusions and future work

This paper presented an investigation of process-induced deformations of aircraft structural components manufactured by RTM.

The property models for epoxy 890 RTM, fibre and laminate unidirectional properties, as well as frictional contact conditions were implemented into Abaqus/COMPRO to predict process-induced deformations generated during the RTM process. Four C-frames were manufactured according to two different cure cycles. The analysis of spring-in and twist through CMM data confirmed that the cure cycle had no significant effect on the deformations.

The experimental values for spring-in and twist showed very good agreement with simulations. In the future, in order to further improve the accuracy of the simulations, the temperature of the mould, mandrel and part should be monitored during the process to use a more accurate simulated cure cycle. Manufacturing defects can also play a large role in part distortions and contribute to larger deformations compared to simulations that assume the part to be perfect.

Nevertheless, the use of such a modeling tool demonstrates potential for industrial purposes to significantly reduce the design time and manufacturing costs with the appropriate tool scheme compensation.

Table 1. Study of cure cycle parameters

Study A	Two step cycle - 120°C (250°F) Intermediate dwell - 180°C (355°F) final cure
Study B	One step cycle - No intermediate dwell - 180°C (355°F) final cure

Fig. 1. Three-part mould for C-frame manufacturing.

Fig. 2. Cross-section model used for part deformation simulations.

Fig. 3. 3D model of the C-frame used for part deformation simulations.

Table 2. Cooldown parameters investigated for part deformation simulations.

Cooldown rate (°C/min)					
0.5	0.7	1.3	1.9	2.6	4.5
Heat transfer coefficient (HTC, W/m²K)					
5 (11-hour cooldown)			50 (2-hour cooldown)		

Fig. 4. Simplified cure cycle used for residual stresses simulations.

Fig. 5. Directions in which CTE was measured by TMA on unidirectional CF/epoxy samples.

Fig. 6. Typical TMA curves for transversal direction on unidirectional NCF/890RTM epoxy sample.

Fig. 7. Typical spring-in observed for C-frame cross-section before (left) and after demoulding (right) for a 2-hour cooldown at 1.3°C/min. Scale deformation factor = 8.

Table 3. C-frame's spring-in values, Δd (mm) and δ ($^\circ$), for different cooldown parameters obtained from 2D simulations.

Cooldown rate ($^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$)						
	0.5	0.7	1.3	1.9	2.6	4.5
$\Delta d=1.04\text{mm}$	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.02	1.02
$\delta=0.91^\circ$	0.91	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.89	0.89
Heat transfer coefficient (HTC, $\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$)						
5 (11-hour cooldown)			50 (2-hour cooldown)			
$\Delta d = 1.05 \text{ mm}, \delta = 0.91^\circ$			$\Delta d = 1.05 \text{ mm}, \delta = 0.91^\circ$			

Fig. 8. Part deformations observed after demoulding and how they were measured: a) spring-in, and b) twist. Scale deformation factor = 10.

Table 4. C-frame measurements for spring-in and twist obtained from 3D simulation after demoulding.

Spring-in, Δd (δ) mm ($^\circ$)		
Δd_1	Δd_2	Δd_3
1.14 (0.99)	0.86 (0.75)	0.91 (0.79)
Twist, θ ($^\circ$)		
2.10		

Fig. 9. C-frame components after a) demoulding and b) trimming.

Fig. 10. 3D CMM measurements reproduced in CATIA for comparison with simulation results. C-sections were measured at five different locations on the outer surface, as numbered above.

Table 5. Average CMM measurements for spring-in and twist obtained on C-frame parts after demoulding/trimming and corresponding simulation results.

Spring-in, Δd (δ)		
mm ($^{\circ}$)		
Δd_1 (δ_1)	Δd_3 (δ_3)	Δd_5 (δ_5)
Experiments		
1.01 ± 0.05 (1.16 ± 0.13)	0.66 ± 0.10 (0.76 ± 0.10)	0.99 ± 0.09 (1.14 ± 0.12)
Simulation		
0.83 (1.08)	0.62 (0.80)	0.67 (0.86)
Twist, θ		
$(^{\circ})$		
Experiments		
1.05 ± 0.22		
Simulation		
1.20		

5 References

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